
The Influence of Motivation as A Mediator Between the Influence of School Leadership Style and Biology Teachers' Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB)

Clavinzky Anggita¹, I Made Putrawan², Supriyatin³

^{1,2,3}Master of Biology Education, State University of Jakarta

ABSTRACT: Teachers are a very important profession in changing the future of the nation. The true successors of the nation are educated students. As the old saying goes, education is a window to see the world more broadly, so a competent professional teacher is needed to guide students to achieve their goals. In order to achieve superior quality biology teachers, it is necessary to have a school leadership style that will influence wise interpersonal behavior or Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) and good motivation in working as a teacher. In overcoming this, a causal survey was used involving 100 biology teachers in East Jakarta. There are three instruments developed to measure leadership style (Reliability coefficient 0.785), Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) (Reliability coefficient 0.842), and motivation (Reliability coefficient 0.816). The research hypothesis was analyzed by path analysis. This study found that leadership style was proven to have a significant direct effect on ICB of biology teachers, ICB of biology teachers was significantly influenced by motivation (path coefficient obtained at 0.110), leadership style had a very significant direct effect on motivation (path coefficient 0.282), motivation had a very significant direct effect on ICB of teachers (path coefficient of 0.311). The results of the indirect effect test of leadership style on ICB of biology teachers through motivation obtained a value of 0.08 which turned out to be insignificant, because the magnitude was close to zero. Even though the indirect effect of leadership style on ICB of teachers was not significant, in total, namely the combination of leadership style and motivation had an effect on ICB of teachers which characterized the combined effect of direct effect and indirect effect of these variables.

KEYWORDS: School Leadership Style, Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior, Motivation, Path Analysis, Biology Teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are a very important profession in the future of the nation. The true successors of the nation are educated students. As the old saying goes, education is a window to see the world more broadly, so a competent professional teacher is needed to guide students to achieve their goals. The competence of a teacher can be seen from the results of teaching and learning activities obtained by students through learning in the classroom or school environment. Based on the test scores obtained by students, it can reflect the abilities possessed by the teacher. One of the science lessons that often gets scores below the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) is biology after chemistry and physics lessons. Biology lessons are often considered difficult by students because they study living organisms, both plants, animals and humans, so they have a lot of material and sub-chapters. The classification of living things has a lot of material accompanied by scientific language that is difficult to understand, has concepts that are difficult to understand, etc. is one of the factors why students get scores that do not match the minimum completion criteria set by the school. Based on students' concerns about biology lessons, teachers must be able to master the teaching materials before teaching, relate scientific concepts to everyday life, be skilled in teaching, reflective, factual, proficient, open, creative and communicative (Lodang, 2013).

In order to achieve superior quality biology teachers, it is necessary to have wise interpersonal behavior or Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) and good motivation in working as teachers. Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) is a dimension of Citizenship Behavior. The dimensions of Citizenship Behavior are organizational and interpersonal. Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior is teacher behavior that makes a positive contribution to the school environment. This behavior is like teachers who like to help students and fellow teachers, teach new things they have and do not hide them for their own interests, maintain a good attitude towards fellow teachers and students even though there are mistakes, do not force their will, are enthusiastic in working, follow the rules that exist in school. This behavior can be formed from good social relationships and communication when interacting with others to form a good relationship. Positive relationships in the work environment will influence individual behavior, such as actively providing suggestions and input and being more motivated at work.

Factors that influence teacher performance are motivation (Handayani, 2019). Motivation in teachers is created because of the drive or desire of a person that arises from outside or within themselves. The dimensions of motivation are to clarify the achievement

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of goals, the desire to be the best, and focus on work (Putrawan, 2017). Motivation can be formed from relationships that exist between individuals who build and trust each other. Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) and motivation are influenced by school leadership. Teachers must exude good interpersonal attitudes and motivation in the school environment, because teachers have a great influence on their followers, namely students. Likewise, the principal who serves as a leader who has a great influence on a teacher's motivation in teaching and in the school environment. According to Yuhana (2021), a leader must have the ability to raise the spirits of his followers, have responsibility, have a positive influence and have the ability to convince his followers. In addition, the role of the principal as a leader must have the ability to gain other involvement in the management process, persuade teachers and staff to balance individual needs and organizational needs, and persuade personnel to pay attention to the breadth of various options (Syafarida, 2015). Leaders have their own leadership types, namely transformational and transactional (Putrawan, 2020). Transformational leadership is a relationship between leaders and followers that arouses enthusiasm and inspires to achieve a goal without any reward (Nurhudan, 2019). Transactional leadership is a reciprocal relationship between leaders and followers in order to achieve a positive goal accompanied by rewards (Putrawan, 2020). If the principal as a leader creates and implements transactional and transformational leadership well, it will certainly influence the behavior of his followers in the school environment.

Based on the explanation above, this study is said to be original because no one has studied teacher behavior (ICB), the high state of the art is a change in behavior, namely adaptive behavior not only in the teaching and learning process but also adaptive to behave in a healthy life, so that the influence of motivation as a mediator between the influence of leadership style and Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) of biology teachers is worthy of being studied.

Based on this, the purpose of writing in this study is to find out: (1) Is it possible that school culture also influences the ICB of biology teachers (2) is it possible that the organizational structure of the school also influences the ICB of biology teachers? (3) doesn't teamwork also influence the ICB of biology teachers (4) Does the personality of biology teachers influence the Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) of teachers through motivation?

METHOD

This study is a quantitative study using a survey method with a causal technique. This method is used to determine the influence of exogenous and endogenous variables, namely two exogenous variables including (1) school leadership style and (2) motivation and endogenous variables are interpersonal citizenship behavior. Path analysis is used to test the direct influence of the variables to be studied. This study used Simple Random Sampling involving 100 biology teachers in East Jakarta. There are three instruments used to measure, namely school leadership style, motivation and interpersonal citizenship behavior which have been measured for validity using Pearson Product Moment and reliability using Cronbach Alpha with the help of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS26).

The interpersonal citizenship behavior measurement instrument consists of 35 statement items measured using the 5-4-3-2-1 interpersonal citizenship behavior scale with 31 valid statements, 4 invalid statements and a reliability of 0.785. The motivation measurement instrument consists of 30 items measured using the 5-4-3-2-1 personality scale with 26 valid statements and 4 invalid statements and a reliability of 0.842. The school leadership style measurement instrument consists of 36 items measured on the 5-4-3-2-1 integrity scale with 34 valid statements and 2 invalid statements and a reliability of 0.816. Data were analyzed by regression, correlation and path analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study was conducted with the aim of determining whether there is an influence between variables with path analysis, namely the direct influence of school leadership style on interpersonal citizenship behavior, the direct influence of school leadership style on motivation, Motivation has a direct effect on Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) of biology teachers and the indirect influence of leadership style on interpersonal citizenship behavior through motivation. This study used the filling of instruments that had been filled by 100 biology teachers in East Jakarta using Google Form. After the validation test and calculating the reliability of the instrument, the next step was to conduct a normality test with the KomolgorovSmirnov test and a homogeneity test with the Bartlett test. Based on the results of the normality test and the homogeneity test, it can be seen that the data is normally distributed and the dependent variable score group and the independent variable group score are homogeneous at a significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Before using the regression equation to draw conclusions in hypothesis testing, the regression model obtained was tested for significance and linearity using the F test and ANOVA. Based on the results of the significance and linearity tests, the regression equation $X_1 = 0.276 + X_2 = 76.474$, $X_3 = 134.191 + 0.120 X_1$, $X_3 = 111.096 + 0.346 X_2$ is significant and linear.

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Table 1 ANOVA for the regression model X1 against X3

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		Part
	B		Std. Error Beta			Zeroorder	Partial	
1 (Constan)	76.474	13.099		5.838	.000			
X1	.276	.095	.282**	2.907	0.01	.282	.282	.282

Dependent Variable: X2; ** P < 0,01

Table 2 ANOVA for the regression model X3 = 134,191 + 0,120 X1

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		Part
	B		Std. Error Beta			ero-order	Partial	
1 (Constant)	134.191	15.109		8.882	.000			
X1	.120	.110	.110*	1.098	0,27	.110	.110	.110

Dependent Variable: X3; * P < 0,27

Table 3 ANOVA for the regression model X3 = 111,096 + 0,346 X2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		Part
	B		Std. Error Beta			Zeroorder	Partial	
1 (Constant)	111.096	12.294		9.037	.000			
X2	.346	.107	.311	3.240**	0.01	.311	.311	.311

Dependent Variable: X3; ** P < 0,01

The next step after the significance and linearity test of the regression equation is the path analysis test. Based on Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3, the empirical model of the path analysis test results can be seen in Figure 1. After obtaining the results of all hypotheses, the empirical model is as follows:

Figure 1. Empirical Research Model

Table 4: Summary of Hypothesis Test Results

Variabel	N	Path Coefficient	Tcal	Ttable (0,05)
X1 & X2	100	0,282	2.907	1.984
X1 & X3	100	0,110	8.882	1.984
X2 & X3	100	0,311	3.240	1.984
X1 ON X3 through X2	100	0,08		1.984

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The results of the study indicate that (1) school leadership style has a significant direct effect on motivation with a path coefficient of $\Phi_{21} = 0.282$ and $t_{count} = 2.907$; (2) school leadership style on interpersonal citizenship behavior with a path coefficient of $\Phi_{32} = 0.110$ and $t_{count} = 8.882$; (3) motivation has a significant direct effect on interpersonal citizenship behavior with a path coefficient of $\Phi_{31} = 0.311$ and $t_{count} = 3.240$; and (4) school leadership style has a significant indirect effect on interpersonal citizenship behavior through motivation with a path coefficient of $\Phi_{31.2} = 0.08$. The summary of the results of the hypothesis testing is presented in Table 4.

Based on the results of the first hypothesis testing, namely the path coefficient in the first hypothesis is proven to have an effect. It is proven that the transactional and transformational school leadership styles that are owned can provide motivation to biology teachers. School leadership style is the activity or behavior of superiors in directing, motivating, inspiring and providing rules but still giving appreciation to their subordinates, namely biology teachers. School leadership style can be a trigger for biology teachers' motivation in achieving their work goals, both in the desire to develop a career/achieve and focus and perseverance in working. This will certainly have a positive impact on biology learning because teachers are motivated to teach biology.

Based on Liberman's research (2015), the leadership of school superiors who build relationships with teachers in working together, appreciate every idea given by teachers to the school causes teachers' trust in making decisions which will increase teachers' intrinsic motivation. Putrawan (2020) stated that leadership style also plays an important role in motivation so that they have goals in working. Based on research by Pratiwi (2023) and Maduningtias (2017), motivation has an important role, because with this motivation it is hoped that each individual will encourage someone to do a certain activity, work hard and be enthusiastic to achieve high productivity.

Based on the second hypothesis research, namely the influence of school leadership style (X1) on the Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) of biology teachers (X3). The results of the school leadership style assessed by biology teachers towards their superiors such as principals, were proven to have a significant direct effect on interpersonal wise behavior or ICB of 0.27 (path coefficient table). It is proven that the transactional and transformational school leadership styles that are possessed can influence the ICB of biology teachers. School leadership style can have an impact on followers, because leadership is a strength of soul and creative moral strength that can influence its members to change/maintain interpersonal attitudes or ICB of biology teachers in East Jakarta. Positive behavior that provides assistance, has a sporty attitude and polite and courteous actions towards colleagues and students is the interpersonal behavior (ICB) of biology teachers.

School leadership style must have a major impact on teacher interpersonal through actions or words, in line with the research of Aboramadan & Kundi (2020) namely a leader must have communication skills to develop a strong emotional bond between the leader and his followers. Because interpersonal behavior (ICB) refers to behavior directed by others, namely a good leadership style will be oriented towards followers because they tend to be considered role models so that it has an impact on the interpersonal behavior (ICB) of followers (LinGuo, 2020). In line with the research of Robbins & Judge (2019) that leadership is stated as a process of influencing and supporting others to do their work in achieving all goals. Based on the theory, the leadership style will affect the interpersonal behavior (ICB) of biology teachers. The results of the path error coefficient obtained by the leadership style (X1) on the Interpersonal Citizenship Behavior (ICB) of biology teachers (X3) are 0.99, which means that it has a path error coefficient that is still very large and it is proven that there are still many factors that are suspected of having a direct influence on the ICB of biology teachers.

Related to the results of testing the third hypothesis of this study, the direct influence of motivation (X2) on interpersonal citizenship behavior (X3) shows a very significant influence and relationship between X2 and X3. The results of this test indicate that not only leadership style is needed in strengthening the wise interpersonal behavior of teachers, especially biology teachers, but also depends on how the motivational profile of the teachers in its influence on the teacher's ICB which from the results of this research has proven to be very influential. The objectives to be achieved are the motivation of biology teachers in terms of direction, intensity, and persistence.

The fourth hypothesis is the indirect influence of leadership style (X1) on interpersonal citizenship behavior (X3) through motivation (X2). Motivation is a mediator considered between school leadership style and interpersonal citizenship behavior. This study obtained a path coefficient of 0.08 which means it is not significant, this can be interpreted that motivation cannot be used as a good mediator variable in mediating leadership style with interpersonal citizenship behavior (ICB) of biology teachers. In the study of Lin & Weqi (2021) stated that motivation is not the main source in influencing ICB. LePine's research (2007) shows that one source of worker motivation comes from a difficulty, namely demands and obstacles to achieving better work results. Karatepe's research (2016) states that the factors that play an important role in influencing ICB are personality or work attitude and resilience in facing work difficulties. In line with the research of Salanova and Ortega (2019), namely the difficulties faced and job demands will affect ICB.

The possibilities that are thought to influence the motivation of biology teachers include, among others, teacher personality, school culture, organizational structure, teamwork, communication, values adopted by the school, and even the abilities possessed

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by the teachers as intrinsic motivation, so that the variance of leadership style becomes small as an element of its influence on teacher ICB. Cavanaugh (2015) who stated that demands are an obstacle to self-development and interpersonal growth. Min (2019) said that boredom at work greatly affects interpersonal behavior. Therefore, Lin & weqi (2021) said the importance of the influence of leadership style on followers' interpersonal through personality.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings above, this thesis concludes that to maintain and care for the interpersonal Citizenship Behavior of biology teachers, which is one of the requirements for their personality competencies to be well organized through interpersonal behavior so that success is expected in carrying out the task of the teaching and learning process, then factors such as their positive assessment of the leadership style of superiors who focus on the transformational style and added to the strength of their motivation, so that these factors cannot be ignored in accordance with the integrity of the theoretical model as part of the organizational behavior model.

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